

Connecting a cantilever to the counter part printed circuit board (PCB)

Recommended equipment:

- A strong metal tweezers with ribs for a better grip

example:
www.rs-online.com
order no. [4986510](#)

SCL recommends to use plastic tweezers to handle silicon chips to prevent chip damaging (e.g. Rubis K2A, Ideatek 702A.DG, etc.).

1. Take the cantilever PCB out of a cantilever box with a metal tweezers. Hold the PCB tightly between the tweezers arms and rotate the PCB slightly when detaching it from the double sided tape.

2. Place the PCB with its male connector exactly on its female counter part PCB (CP-PCB) connector.

3. Turn the tweezers and use the tweezers backside to press gently down the cantilever towards the CP-PCB connector. The two connectors must fit exactly for a stable connection.

Disconnecting the cantilever:

Take the cantilever tightly with the tweezers and pull it straight up.